

WWJMRD 2022; 8(11): 91-94
www.wwjmr.com
International Journal
Peer Reviewed Journal
Refereed Journal
Indexed Journal
Impact Factor SJIF 2017:
5.182 2018: 5.51, (ISI) 2020-
2021: 1.361
E-ISSN: 2454-6615

Ariel de Figueiredo Nogueira Mesquita, João Moreira de Matos Neto

Biotechnology Student (undergraduate) – Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology - Federal University of Ceará – Fortaleza - Brazil.

Leonardo Lima Bandeira

Graduate Student in Ecology and Natural Resources – Federal University of Ceará – Fortaleza - Brazil

Fernando Gouveia Cavalcante

PhD in Ecology and Natural Resources – Federal University of Ceará – Fortaleza - Brazil

Suzana Claudia Silveira

Martins, Claudia Miranda Martins

Microbiology Professor at Biology Department – Laboratory of Environmental Microbiology – Federal University of Ceará – Fortaleza – Brazil.

Correspondence:

Ariel de Figueiredo Nogueira Mesquita

Biotechnology Student (undergraduate) – Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology - Federal University of Ceará – Fortaleza - Brazil.
arielmesquita26@alu.ufc.br

Amylase-Producing Actinobacteria Facilitate Rhizobia Growth in a Culture Medium with Starch

Ariel de Figueiredo Nogueira Mesquita, Leonardo Lima Bandeira, Fernando Gouveia Cavalcante, João Moreira de Matos Neto, Suzana Claudia Silveira Martins, Claudia Miranda Martins

Abstract

Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) are microorganisms that act in the production of metabolites that confer advantages for the growth and development of the plant, receiving in exchange sources of carbon and energy. Two classic examples of PGPR are rhizobia, which act in the bioavailability of nitrogen, and actinobacteria, which perform numerous functions such as production of phytohormones, antibiotics, and solubilization of phosphate and potassium. To establish this microbiota, the plant releases carbohydrate-rich exudates that not only serve as a carbon source for microorganisms, but also determine which microorganisms can colonize its rhizosphere. This study evaluated how amylase-producing actinobacteria are able to allow rhizobia growth without this enzymatic activity when co-inoculated in a culture medium that has starch as the sole carbon source. Since starch is a carbohydrate like those released in exudates, it is inferred that this ability to facilitate growth *in vitro* would be important in stimulating rhizobia growth in the rhizosphere and, consequently, nitrogen fixation. Ten actinobacteria and seven rhizobia were used, of which we obtained 12.86% of positive results. This cooperation exemplifies another case of substrate cross-feeding, paving the way to further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies of interbacterial interactions, as well as to the prospect of biofertilizers.

Keywords: Bacterial ecological interactions; Bioinoculant; Cross-Feeding; PGPR; *Streptomyces*.

1. Introduction

Microorganisms play numerous ecological roles in soil, such as changing the spatial distribution and bioavailability of nutrients [1]. Bacteria beneficial to plants are traditionally known as plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) and act in the mobilization of nutrients in the soil, production of growth regulators, phytohormones, solubilization of phosphate and potassium, and protection against phytopathogens [2].

Plant growth, productivity, and health rely on the microbial community associated with it, so the plant shapes the composition of the rhizospheric microbiota via rhizosphere feedback. Exudates are rich in carbohydrates, amino acids, organic acids, flavonoids, growth factors, enzymes, among others, which vary from plant to plant due to genetic and environmental factors, and are capable of selecting and stimulating microbial growth [3, 4, 5]. In association with factors such as soil type and pH, exudates determine the nature of the local microbiota [6].

The release of flavonoids from roots attracts bacteria known as rhizobia. These bacteria are the most classic example of PGPR due to its capacity of forming symbiotic nodules in the roots of legumes. There, they perform biological nitrogen fixation, which is a process responsible for making this nutrient bioavailable to the plant [7].

Exudates also attract other PGPRs such as actinobacteria. These bacteria stimulate plant growth, antagonize phytopathogens, improve nutrient availability, and produce phytohormones such as auxins and gibberellins [8]. Outside the rhizospheric environment, actinobacteria also show great biotechnological value for the production of antibiotics, insecticides, herbicides, immunomodulators, and enzymes such as cellulases, xylanases, pectinases, proteases, chitinases and amylases [9].

In this study, we evaluated the ability of actinobacteria with amylolytic activity to facilitate the growth of rhizobia without this enzymatic activity when grown in solid media with starch as sole carbon source. Microorganisms in the rhizosphere are fed by plant exudates and among the carbon sources present in this compound are carbohydrates, such as starch. Therefore, the ability of rhizobacteria such as actinobacteria to allow the growth of PGPR as rhizobia in the presence of this sugar constitutes an important ecological relationship and is the focus of this research.

2. Materials and methods

The microorganisms studied in this work were selected based on their extracellular amylolytic activity from the culture collection of the Laboratory of Environmental Microbiology of the Federal University of Ceará. We used ten strains of actinobacteria with extracellular amylolytic activity statistically different from the others, and 7 strains of rhizobia without this enzymatic activity. The actinobacteria genus was identified by Ribeiro et al. [10], and the species of rhizobia by Silva [11]. This information is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Strains of actinobacteria and Rhizobia from the Semi-arid used in this work.

Actinobacteria		Rhizobia	
Strain	Genus	Strain	Species
A108	<i>Streptomyces</i>	L1	<i>Bradyrhizobium elkanii</i>
A109	<i>Nocardia</i>	L4	<i>Bradyrhizobium elkanii</i>
A125	<i>Streptomyces</i>	L9	<i>Rhizobium tropici</i>
A136	<i>Streptomyces</i>	L13	<i>Bradyrhizobium kavangense</i>
A139	<i>Streptomyces</i>	L15	<i>Bradyrhizobium japonicum</i>
A143	<i>Streptomyces</i>	L24	<i>Bradyrhizobium yuanmingense</i>
A144	<i>Streptosporangium</i>	L27	<i>Bradyrhizobium iriomotense</i>
A145	<i>Streptomyces</i>	-	-
A146	<i>Streptosporangium</i>	-	-
A148	<i>Streptomyces</i>	-	-

Source: Ribeiro *et al.* (2022); Silva (2020).

Co-inoculation was performed according to Silva *et al.* [12] with modifications. The actinobacteria were inoculated by spots in duplicate in a culture medium containing starch as the sole carbon source. The plates were then incubated in a B.O.D. incubator for 7 days at 28°C.

At the end of the actinobacterial incubation period, 1 ml of rhizobia cultured in YM broth (yeast extract-mannitol) was transferred to sterile microtubes in triplicate. The microtubes were centrifuged at 9261 x g for 10 minutes. The supernatant was discarded and the pellet resuspended 3 times in sterile distilled water. 10 µL of purified rhizobia were then transferred to the plates containing the actinobacteria grown in starch medium, approximately 1 cm from the actinobacteria colony. The plates were then incubated in a B.O.D. incubator at 28°C for another 7 days. Rhizobium growth characterized a positive result, while the

absence of growth characterized a negative result. The compatibility index (CI) of actinobacteria and rhizobia was calculated by the ratio between the number of positive pairs and the number of possible pairs for each strain.

3. Results & Discussion

Among the 70 possible pairs, 9 presented a positive result, which represents 12.86% of positive pairs. Actinobacteria A148 stood out from the others, presenting a compatibility index of 0.429. Rhizobia L1 showed a compatibility index of 0.4, the highest among all rhizobia studied, and was compatible even with actinobacteria A148. Therefore, it is concluded that the pair A148+L1 is the most promising. The results are summarized in Table 2. Some examples of positive pairs are illustrated in Figure 1.

Table 2: *In vitro* co-inoculation between Semiarid actinobacteria and rhizobia in medium with starch.

Rhizobia	Actinobacteria										RCI
	A108	A109	A125	A136	A139	A143	A144	A145	A146	A148	
L1	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	0,4
L4	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	0,2
L9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
L13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
L15	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	0,1
L24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
L27	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	0,2
ACI	0	0	0,143	0	0,286	0,143	0	0,143	0,143	0,429	

(+) presence of facilitation (positive result). (-) absence of facilitation (negative result). (ACI) actinobacterial compatibility index. (RCI) rhizobia compatibility index. Source: the author.

Fig. 1: Examples of positive pairs from *in vitro* coinoculation. The blue arrows indicate rhizobia colonies. Red arrows indicate actinobacterial colonies. The images of A148 actinobacterium present a yellow background, as the intense production of pigments by the strain colored the entire medium. Source: the author.

Even though bacteria commonly compete for nutrients with each other, more complex relationships can be established. One of them is substrate cross-feeding, an interaction in which a strain feeds on molecules produced by the metabolic apparatus of another strain. These molecules can usually be exploited by both strains. An example would be the partial degradation of oligofructose or inulin by *Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron* in coculture with bifidobacteria. Single-chain sugars resulting from this extracellular degradation serve as a carbon source for both strains [13].

There is also evidence that the production of LdhA lactate dehydrogenase by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which reduces pyruvate to D-lactate under anaerobic conditions, enables cross-feeding in biofilms in cystic fibrosis patients. This enzyme would be responsible for producing D-lactate in the anaerobic zone of the biofilm, which would be used as a substrate in the aerobic zone. This cooperation is one of the reasons why it is so complicated to treat patients with this type of lung infection [14]. We co-inoculated amylolytic actinobacteria and non-amylolytic rhizobia in culture medium containing starch as the sole carbon source. Extracellular degradation of starch by actinobacteria, mainly by the A148 strain, allowed the growth of rhizobia in this culture medium in a new example of substrate cross-feeding.

According to Zheng et al. [15], the presence of α -amylase strongly influences the adaptation strategies of bacterial metabolism and stimulates the production of metabolic signals such as acetic acid. This acid induces numerous changes in the physicochemical properties of the bacterial surface, such as hydrophobicity and surface charge, which directly affects the interactions that these bacteria are able to establish. This may explain why only 12.86% of our pairs were positive. As all strains of actinobacteria in this study are amylase producers and the rhizobia are not, the production of this enzyme by the actinobacteria may have influenced the production of other metabolites that inhibited the rhizobia growth. This makes the presence of positive results even more surprising, which can be explained by the production of secondary metabolites by the actinobacteria itself [16] or by the biochemical apparatus of rhizobia [17].

4. Conclusions

The actinobacteria allowing the growth of non-amylase-producing rhizobia in the medium containing starch is an

interaction that exhibits great biotechnological potential for the creation of new biofertilizers, as well as for a better understanding of the ecological relationships that occur in the soil of the Brazilian semiarid region.

5. Acknowledgments

We thank Dr. Francisca Soares de Araújo and the Chico Mendes Institute for the opportunity to carry out the collection of soil samples and consequent isolation of bacterial groups. We would like to also thank CAPES for their assistance during the graduate program.

References

1. Yang, Xiaodong et al. Influence of soil microorganisms and physicochemical properties on plant diversity in an arid desert of Western China. *Journal of Forestry Research*, 2021; 32(6): 2645-2659.
2. Prasad, Mahendra et al. Chapter Seven - Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) for sustainable agriculture: Perspectives and Challenges. *PGPR Amelioration in Sustainable Agriculture*, Woodhead Publishing, 2019, 129-157.
3. Hakim, Sughra et al. Rhizosphere engineering with plant growth-promoting microorganisms for agriculture and ecological sustainability. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 2021; 5: 617157.
4. Tian, Tao et al. The role of rhizodeposits in shaping rhizomicrobiome. *Environmental Microbiology Reports*, 2019; 12(2): 160-172.
5. Vives-Peris, Vicente et al. Root exudates: from plant to rhizosphere and beyond. *Plant Cell Reports*, 2019; 39(1): 3-17.
6. Kopecky, Jan et al. Micronutrients and soil microorganisms in the suppression of potato common scab. *Agronomy*, 2021; 11(2): 383.
7. Routray, Soumya et al. A review on Rhizobia and PGPRs interactions in legumes. *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 2021; 7(10): 1448-1457.
8. Fatmawati, Umi et al. Screening and characterization of actinomycetes isolated from soybean rhizosphere for promoting plant growth. *Biodiversitas Journal of Biological Diversity*, 2019; 20(10): 2970-2977.
9. Gohain, Anwesha et al. Chapter 9 - Actinobacteria: diversity and biotechnological applications. *Recent Advancements in Microbial Diversity*, Academic Press, 2020, 217-231.

10. Ribeiro, Gabrielly et al. In vitro antagonism of actinobacteria against rhizobia from the soil. *Enciclopédia Biosfera*, 2022; 19(41): 41-50.
11. Silva, Valéria Borges da. Polyphasic characterization of nodule endophytic microorganisms of *Vigna* spp. grown in soils of Caatinga biome. Areia, PB. Universidade Federal da Paraíba, Centro de Ciências Agrárias – CCA. Thesis. September, 2020. Graduate program of Soil Science.
12. Silva, Valéria Maria Araujo et al. Cross-Feeding Among Soil Bacterial Populations: selection and characterization of potential bio-inoculants. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 2019; 11(5): 23.
13. Smith, Nick W. et al. The Classification and Evolution of Bacterial Cross-Feeding. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 2019; 7: 1-15.
14. Lin, Yu-Cheng et al. The *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Complement of Lactate Dehydrogenases Enables Use of d - and l -Lactate and Metabolic Cross-Feeding. *Mbio*, 2018; 9(5): 1-12.
15. Zheng, Tongtong et al. Improvement of α -amylase to the metabolism adaptations of soil bacteria against PFOS exposure. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 2021; 208: 111770.
16. Boubekri, Kenza et al. Multifunctional role of Actinobacteria in agricultural production sustainability: a review. *Microbiological Research*, 2022; 261: 127059.
17. Fang, Linchuan et al. Exogenous application of signaling molecules to enhance the resistance of legume-rhizobium symbiosis in Pb/Cd-contaminated soils. *Environmental Pollution*, 2020; 265: 114744.